

Quantum Spin, Inner Product and Lost Information

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Some problems only require a certain amount of information for their solution. For example, a photon refracting from a medium interface along the x axis problem may be solved by noting that momentum and speed in medium 1 are pn_1 and c/n_1 (where p, c are momentum and speed in a vacuum and n_1 is the index of refraction). In medium n_2 , one replaces n_1 with n_2 . From these classical smooth values (deterministic values) one may obtain Snell's law which may be verified experimentally.

What happens if one takes this same information and tries to solve for the relative probabilities of reflection/refraction for a photon moving along the x axis in a medium with n_1 and hitting an interface along the y axis at $x=0$. The medium for $x>0$ has $n_2>n_1$. Can this problem be solved simply using $E=pc$, and pn_i , c/n_i ? It seems it cannot. Furthermore, the smooth pn_i and c/n_i appear to be approximations because the speed of light in a medium changes due to interactions with atoms. One might expect some type of stochastic behaviour, as a result, with pn_i and c/n_i being averages. As shown in (1), one may maximize Shannon's entropy subject to periodic constraints to find an unusual two-dimensional probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. This probability allows one to find relative probabilities for reflection/refraction and also predicts/solves a n-slit interference-diffraction problem. Thus the smoothed over pn_i and c/n_i information is not wrong, but only solves certain problems. More information is given by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which may be used to solve further problems.

Given that we suggest $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ follows from two maximizations of Shannon's entropy, one for $P(x)$ and one for $P(t)$, one might expect there is no further information. We suggest, however, that for $t \rightarrow t + \text{constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \text{constant}/p$, $-Et+px$ does not change and this result should hold as seen in any frame moving at constant average v (velocity). By mentioning average v , one already takes a deterministic view and approximates the stochasticity of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In (1), we argued that one may find the specific transformation involved in viewing E, p, x, t from a moving frame and that not only is $-Et+px$ invariant, but also $-tt+xx$ and $-EE+pp$.

In fact, $-EE+pp=m^2$ ($c=1$) is a relation between E and p as well as being an inner product. We argue here that an inner product, in general, loses information as it is a relative relationship between two vectors. A point we wish to make is that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a solution of $-EE+pp=m^2$ ($c=1$) if one replaces E with $i\partial/\partial t$ partial and p with $-i\partial/\partial x$ partial. Thus, we suggest some information is lost. There is no reason to require a second order differential equation when a first order one yields p and E , although the second order equation is not wrong, it just removes some information as does an average. We thus suggest that Dirac's approach to finding a linear equation in $i\partial/\partial t$ partial and $-i\partial/\partial x$ partial is an attempt to retrieve this extra information.

This approach applies to finding extra information called spin, which again, is only useful in certain problems (for example, when a magnetic field is present). In (2) we examined a continuity equation with the Poynting vector and energy density $(\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{B})$ (Electric field Electric field + $\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ Magnetic field Magnetic field) and showed it may also be broken into two linear equations which yield spin 1 information. Thus we argue that certain equations (quadratic in nature) may represent a loss of information, especially those that represent a kind of coarse grained average

as in the case of energy density or even classical probability to reflect or refract. In such a case, one may try to linearize in order to find this lost information.

Refracting -Reflecting Photon

Given a reflection-refraction of light problem, one may immediately find the angle of reflection by assuming: p_y before = $-p_y$ after and p_x before = p_x after for an interface along the x axis. This approach assumes smooth deterministic motion i.e. the photon has an exact classical momentum and speed. This same determinism applies to the description of the refracted ray. One again assumes that p_x before = p_x after, but p_{n1} and $c/n1$ are the overall momentum and speed in $n1$ (index of refraction) in medium 1 and p_{n2} and $c/n2$ in medium $n2$. From this smooth deterministic information, one may derive Snell's law which is experimentally verifiable.

One may thus think that smooth deterministic information is all that is needed to solve reflection refraction problems. It seems, however, that c/n_i differs from c , the speed in a vacuum, due to interactions with the atoms in the medium and this seems to be a stochastic process. Thus p_{ni} and c/n_i may be average values which lose some information. In (1) we argue that one may maximize Shannon's entropy subject to periodic constraints $\int p(x) P(x)$ and $\int P(t) P(t)$ in order to find the two-dimensional probabilities:

$$P(x) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad P(t) = \exp(-iEt) \quad ((1b))$$

What problems do ((1a)) and ((1b)) solve and are the results experimentally verifiable? First, there is case of the interference-diffraction patterns created by light interacting with a n -slit system, with slit separations being on the order of \hbar/p . This pattern cannot be predicted or explained by using smooth values of p_{ni} and c/n_i , even though these are perfectly fine for deriving Snell's law. Secondly, one cannot find the relative probabilities for reflection-refraction for a photon moving in the x direction which hits an interface $n1$ - $n2$ along the y-axis at $x=0$. The form $\exp(ipx)$ is required to solve this problem. One assumes $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx)$ for the incident and reflected photon and $C \exp(ip2x)$ for the refracted one.

$$\text{At } x=0 \quad A+B=C \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{Creating a momentum balance equation yields: } pA-Bp=Cp2 \quad ((2b))$$

Two equations with A known allow one to solve for B,C.

One may, however, multiply ((2a)) and ((2b)) to obtain:

$$AAp = pBB + p2CC \quad ((3))$$

Using $E=pc$ with E being the same for the incident, reflected and refracted photon, yields:

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c2 \quad ((4))$$

If AA, BB, CC are interpreted as fluxes, then AA/c is the number of incident photons, BB/c the number of reflected and $CC/c2$ the number of refracted. There is nothing wrong with ((4)). It is a

basic conservation of photon number (and energy equation if one multiplies by E). The issue is that this equation loses information, namely the information contained in the two separate ((2a)) ((2b)) equations which are ultimately linked with $\exp(ipx)$. Given certain equations like ((4)), one may need to break them into linear factors, although in the case of ((4)) that might not be immediately evident.

The Case of an Inner Product Losing Information

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ was argued in (1) to follow from two maximizations of Shannon's entropy subject to periodic constraints. One may at first think that there is no further information to obtain. Given that E and p are smooth deterministic values with the probability distributions being in t and x, one may suspect that some information is missing. This becomes clearer when one considers $-Et+px$ and notes that $t \rightarrow t + \text{constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \text{constant}/p$ leave the value unchanged. This should hold as viewed from any frame moving with constant v. A constant v, however, is a smooth deterministic value i.e. an average value, so it is possible that one is not dealing with full information.

If one considers a transformation taking (p,E) or (x,t) and converting it to (p',E') or (x',t') as seen from a frame moving at velocity -v (in the x direction) then $-Et+px$ is an inner product and is invariant. One may, however, create the inner products $-tt+xx$ and $-EE+pp$. In the latter case:

$$-EE+pp = m^2 c^2 \quad ((5))$$

We argue, however, that inner products lose information as they are a relative measure between two vectors. What does ((5)) have to do with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$? $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a solution of ((5)) if one replaces E with $i\partial/\partial t$ partial and p with $-i\partial/\partial x$ partial. We argue that the form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ may not describe the full information in the problem. Like with the quadratic form ((4)) one might be able to find extra information (related to extra stochasticity) by linearizing ((5)). This is exactly what Dirac did. We suggest, however, that there is a specific reason for doing this, namely that ((5)) loses some information in the problem. This information is stochastic in the form of something called spin and related to Pauli matrices. ((5)) leads to spin information for spin $1/2$. What happens in the photon case for which spin is 1?

Photon Spin

In the case of a photon, one again has $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which follows from the maximization of two Shannon's entropies subject to periodic constraints. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, however, is also linked to a continuity equation in average energy, momentum conservation equation using the Poynting vector i.e.

$$\frac{d}{dt} (.5\epsilon_0 E^2 + .5/\mu_0 B^2) + \text{grad dot } 1/\mu_0 E \times B = 0 \quad \text{where } E = \text{electric field and } B = \text{magnetic field} \quad ((6))$$

This equation is quadratic with electric and magnetic fields being perpendicular vectors, but behaving as $\text{Real}(\exp(-iEt+ipx))$. The quadratic equation is a combined vector equation

(possibly related to averages) and lost information. In (2) we show that it may be linearized with the Levi-Civita symbol $\epsilon(ijk)$ playing the role of the Pauli matrices for this spin 1 case. Thus we suggest that for the third time ((4)), ((5)) and now ((6)), one has quadratic equations which lose information and need to be linearized to find new information. In these cases, the information is stochastic. In ((4)), one finds new information linked with $\exp(ipx)$, while in ((5)) and ((6)) one finds spin information.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that some problems only require certain information. For example, a physically stochastic problem may be associated with certain average values. These may be enough to solve certain problems. For example, Snell's law may be derived using the notion of a smooth, average p/n and speed c/n . These appear as deterministic values because they are average, but the photon really undergoes stochastic motion by interaction with atoms in the medium. We point out that the average values p/n and c/n do not solve all problems. They do not predict or solve n -slit diffraction-interference nor do they solve for relative reflection-refraction probabilities for a photon moving in the x direction and reaching a media interface n_1-n_2 along the y axis at $x=0$. $\exp(ipx)$ is needed to solve this problem.

We noted in (1) that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ may be obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to periodic constraints. Here we point out that for a problem with two unknowns i.e. reflection and refraction probabilities, one needs two equations. These two equations may be obtained using $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip2x)$ at $x=0$ where A represents the incident photon, B the reflected and C the refracted. A momentum balance yields the second equation i.e. one has $A+B=C$ and $pA-pB=C$. One may multiply the two together to obtain a single equation which does not reveal the information contained in the two equations i.e. the hidden $\exp(ipx)$. This product equation, however, is a perfectly fine physical equation. $AAp = BBp + CCp^2$ is equivalent to $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c^2$, which in turn is: number of incident photons = number of reflected + number of refracted, if AA, BB, CC represent fluxes. Thus information, in particular stochastic information may be hidden in a quadratic type equation, inner products being one of these.

If one considers the case of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ obtained from maximization of Shannon's entropies, one may think there is no extra information, but $-Et+px$ is a quadratic form which we argue is linked with a dot product (invariant special relativistic form). $-EE+pp=mom$ ($c=1$) is another such invariant which yields the solution $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ if $E \rightarrow id/dt$ partial and $p \rightarrow -i d/dx$ partial. Thus one may suggest linearizing this equation, as Dirac did, to find the hidden information i.e. spin. In the case of the photon, it is a continuity equation with energy density with the Poynting vector which is quadratic and hides information. In (2) we linearize to show spin 1 exists with the Levi-Civita symbol (linked to the cross product) describing the spin 1 matrices.

References

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